

**KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICE OF DRUG ABUSE AMONG COMMERCIAL
MOTOR DRIVERS IN PORT HARCOURT METROPOLIS, RIVERS STATE**

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Abstract

This study assessed the knowledge and practice of drug abuse among commercial motor drivers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The research design used was descriptive survey. The population for this study was 500 registered commercial motor drivers (CMDs). A sample size of 300 drivers was purposively taken for the study. A validated self-structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. Reliability indices were obtained for knowledge ($r=0.72$) and practice ($r=0.68$). Analysis of the data was done using a frequency table, percentage and analysis of variance for test statistics. Findings were that CMDs had good knowledge of problems associated with drug abuse. There was no significant difference in knowledge of drug abuse among commercial motor drivers based on age and educational qualification. However, there was significant difference in knowledge of drug abuse among commercial motor drivers based on experience. There was no significant difference in the practice of commercial motor drivers towards drug abuse based on age and educational status. However, there was significant difference in the practice of commercial motor drivers towards drug abuse based on years of experience. This study is expected to create new research areas on drug abuse and its effects. It was, therefore, recommended that commercial motor drivers should be advised to minimize the rate at which they use drugs to aid driving. The CMDs should not take alcohol shortly before and while driving. There should be training of CMDs on the dangers of using drugs while driving and legislation guiding sales of drug should be enforced. Public health workers and Road Safety Corps officials should regularly embark on enlightenment campaign against misuse of drugs by CMDs.

Keywords: Knowledge, practice, commercial motor drivers, drug abuse, Port Harcourt.